

COVID -19 and Its Impact on Different Sectors of Indian & Odisha Economy

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 is a disease caused by a new strain of corona virus "CO" stands for Corona, 'VI' for virus, and 'D' for disease. Formerly, this disease was referred to as '2019 novel Corona virus' or '2019-nCov', on February 11, 2020, the WHO announced an official name for the disease that is causing the 2019 novel corona virus outbreak. The new name of the disease is Corona virus disease 2019, abbreviated as Covid-19. The entire world is in the clutch of Corona virus. The dissemination of the virus is so colossal that it compelled the world health organization (WHO) to declare it is pandemic. The Outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic is an unprecedented shock to the Indian economy. The economy was already in a parlous state before Covid-19 Struck. With the prolonged country wide lockdown, global economic down turn and associated disruption of demand and supply chains, the economy is likely to face a protracted period of slowdown. The magnitude of the economic impact will depend upon the duration and severity of the health crisis the duration of the lockdown and the manner in which the situation unfolds once the lockdown is lifted. This paper depicts impact of Covid-19 On different sectors of Indian Economy; assess the potential impact of the shock on various segments of the economy analyses the policies that have been announced so far by the central government and RBI to ameliorate. The economic shock and put forward a set of policy recommendations for specific sectors.

KEYWORDS: COVID19, Impact on various sectors, policy framework for economic revival, Future hope

INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of Novel Corona virus disease is a grave menace to the entire world affecting millions of people. Besides being detrimental to human health, it also have negative repercussions on the global business world roiling the entire economic system and upending trade and commerce. The outburst of the diseases was first identified in Wuhan, china in 8 December 2019. World Health Organization (WHO) has been thoroughly monitoring and assessing its global hazards, thus declaring it as a Public Health Emergency of international concern on 30th January 2020. The virus started disseminating at an unprecedented rate in different countries across the globe compelling WH to proclaim it as pandemic on 11th March 2020. Now the whole world is grappling with this useable pernicious enemy. Most of the countries are under lockdown and everything including normal life, social and economic conditions seem to grinding to a halt.

In India, the first case of corona virus disease was reported in Kerala on January 30, 2020. Multiple cases were than reported in different cities in India. Hence, the Government of India took necessary action by announcing lockdown in every corner of the country on

How to cite this paper: Shri Ashok Kumar Panda | Shri Arun Kumar Tripathy "COVID -19 and Its Impact on Different Sectors of Indian & Odisha Economy" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-5 | Issue-2, February 2021, pp.1228-1234,

URL:
www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd47822.pdf

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IJTSRD47822

24th March 2020. The metropolises of Delhi, Mumbai, Ahmadabad, Kolkata, Chennai are densely populated which has given rise to a spurt in cases of Covid-19 and these cities are the engines for growth and development of Indian economy. The pandemic has led to socioeconomic disruption, inhibiting the growth of entire economic environment I have been pondering many questions in my mind like will COVID-19 change the way world works, will things go back to normal as before COVID-19, what will be the fundamental change take place in common public, business people, industrialists, and economies. The next few months will be very crucial. We have to alter the concept of normal in this pandemic. If past trends of similar infections are analyzed, it can be helpful to bring any conclusion as to what we should be due to move forwards. How can we overcome this pandemic? Either through mass vaccination or social distancing. What type of life are we expecting in the time of Covid-19? In simple words, I can express that liquidity is expected to reduce as the borrowing cost in real terms will be increased. Though, RBI is continuously making an effort to soften interest rates. Commercial banks and financial institutions are tensed due to the fear of insolvency, NPAs and bankruptcies increase

very much. The focus and stress of government will be to meet out the hyper demand for necessity goods. In contract, business owner of luxurious and comforts goods will stress on covering their outstanding money amount due from debtors. Mergers and partnerships will not take place in this pandemic period when everyone is bearing enormous losses. Thus in this article, an attempt is made to identify the potential impacts of Corona virus on different sectors of Indian Economy.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

The whole world is in the clutch of Corona virus. The impact of the virus being severe and swifter, the government needs to deal with this situation by framing proper strategies in order to survive this hard time. The objective of the study is to focus on the impact of corona virus (Covid-19) on various sectors of the Indian Economy. The Sectoral analysis has also helped to the present scenario of the Indian Economy at that time of Covid-19 pandemic period . The main objective of this paper is to study the spillover effects of Covid-19 on the economy among various sectors. Therefore, the objectives of this study are:

1. To focus on the impact of a corona virus (Covid-19) pandemic on the different sectors of the Indian & Odisha economy.
2. To reflect the need for policy intervention.

Research Methodology:

This part of the research furnishes the research methodology used in this study. This study considers December 2019 to January 2021 as its study period. The review uses secondary data. The data is collected through various magazines, newspapers, and government website for this study. This study focuses on descriptive research design. The sample design chooses for this study is illustrative.

Impact of Corona Virus on Different Sectors of the Indian Economy

The Corona virus has become a major humanitarian challenge and requires a lot of sacrifices to combat the disease. It has been declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the virus continues to spread rapidly around the world through myriad active centers of the transmission. The disease is highly transmissible and disproportionately affects those with underlying conditions. It has led to a global breakdown and affected almost all major countries of the world bringing a slowdown and recession in the economy due to consistent lockdowns by the nations. Covid-19 has set foot in India and is heading the nation to major downturn. Corona virus disease has become a world-changing event and is not only a humanitarian crisis but also economic and social crisis. Its impact on the business environment is worldwide and manifold. Due to the rapid spread of corona virus, several entities are bound to limit their business operations leading to disruption in the economic activities of several industries that drives growth.

The research is being carried out by different organizations and researchers to predict the financial and economic health of the nation in the near future but it is still at an early and rampant stage. The health as well as wealth is both important pillars for the economy to survive and flourish and hence, steps are being taken to improve the

health conditions and financial conditions by launching support schemes and booster plans for various sectors of the Economy. The setback that is being encountered by the different sectors of the economy is highlighted below. .

Primary Sector:

The primary sector includes all those activities the end purpose of which consists in exploiting natural resources. Agriculture, fishing, forestry, mining, deposits. Primary sector encompasses industries associated with extraction and production of raw materials. This sector provides employment to about 43.21% of the population in Indian and contributes about 16.1% of the Indian GDP. It supplies raw materials to secondary sector and furnishes basic necessities of human life.

Agricultural Industry

In agricultural is considered the backbone of the Indian Economy. In agricultural sector, due to travel restrictions for lockdown, there has been a dearth production. Also the pandemic lockdown period coincides with the harvesting seasons of 'Rabi' crop, but owing to paucity of laborers the crops unabatedly stays in the field. As the operations of the business like hotels, restaurants, sweet shops and tea shops are suspended, the market of raw materials which are used for the purpose has gone down leading to grievances of farmers. There is a significant fall in revenue of the tea based industries as they export a substantial part of their output which is now barred.

Secondary Sector

The secondary sector covers all those activities consisting in varying degrees of processing of raw materials (manufacturing construction-industries). The Secondary sector provides employment to around 24.89% of the population in India and contributes about 29.6% of the Indian GDP. It embraces industries that produces and distributes finished goods or indulged in construction activities, thus providing support to both the primary and service sector.

Manufacturing industries

Manufacturing industries are bearing the brunt of corona virus as they had terminated their production at a short notice. The value of the inventories that are held up in the production centers or warehouse of these industries has gone down and the machineries are too lying idle for a long time. Major hindrance encountered by the industries is cash flow constrains and supply chain disruption.

Automobile industries

With almost all plants shut and imports being sealed up, there is a steep decline in production and sales of the automobile companies impelling them to declare pay cuts. The situation will be awful even during post lockdown period due to fall in income levels. Textile and Apparel industry: This industry is workplace for over 45 million people in the country but temporary closure of production units has increased their hurdles leading to lay-offs. The termination of exports and imports have adverse impact on the spinning mills in India as the exports of fabric, yarn and other materials have disrupted.

Pharmaceutical and Chemical Industries

These industries highly count on import of bulk drugs and several raw materials from China. Due to import restrictions these industries are also impacted.

Electronic industry:

The finish products plus the raw materials used in this industry is mainly supplied by China. The spread of corona virus have pushed down the production and sale of electronic goods and the supply chain is also interrupted.

Solar power industry:

Solar power project boulders depend on Chinese imports. Around 80% of solar modules and solar cell used in India are from Chinese manufactures. Thus, the Indian solar project developers started confronting shortage of raw materials and have limited stocks.

Construction and engineering industries:

For construction and engineering industries, the physical presence of massive labour force is essential which is restrained during lockdown and the construction activities have also halted. Thus the industries are tormenting at the hands of ruthless corona virus.

Service Sector

The service sector, also known as the tertiary Sector, is the third tier in the three sector economy. Instead of the product production, this sector produces services maintenance and repairs, training, or consulting. Examples of service Sector jobs include housekeeping, tours. Nursing & teaching etc About 31.9% of the Indian population is employed in service sector which contributes about 54.3 % of the Indian GDP.

Tourism and Hospitality Industries

Tourism and hospitality are the foremost industries to be severely affected amid corona virus crisis and will also be rearmost one to behold resumption of activities. Lockdown has averted the inflow of tourists dealing a crippling blow to the tourism and hospitality industries.

Transportation Segment

The pandemic has put down this segment under massive financial strain. Airlines, cruise and road cargo operators has been struck hard because of border closure and travel restrictions. Some of the aviation companies are not even in the position to refund their customers those who had booked flights that were cancelled due to lockdown.

Health Care Segment

According to FICCI, healthcare segment is at the epicenter of these worldwide pandemic ordeal. Certain public hospitals have witnessed increase in demand in the crisis period. The private hospitals have arisen to the occasion by providing the government with all the succor it requires.

IT Segment

IT segment is reeling under coronavirus crisis as there is immense dwindle in global deal activities as well as growth rate. They are downsizing their work force to tussle with the presence scenario.

Media and Entertainment Industry

Corona virus has compelled to postpone release of several movies shootings have come to rest and the theatres cannot screen movies bringing about heavy loss to this industry.

Banking Segment

The Indian banking system consists of 20 public sector banks, 22 private sector banks, 44 foreign banks, 44 regional rural banks, 1,542 urban cooperative banks and 94,384 rural cooperative banks, to boot to cooperative

credit establishments. As per the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), India's banking sector is sufficiently capitalized and well -regulated. To ensure safety of people amidst the covid-19 outbreak, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) governor, Shaktikanta Das, asked customers to use digital banking facilities as much as possible also added, "In the context of COVID 19, RBI and the government together are giving emphasis on encouraging digital payments. And over a period of time, several measures have already been taken to establish a safe, secure, stable and affordable retail payment system such as the National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) and the immediate payment service (IMPS)". He was speaking at a press conference where he declared mummery measures to address the impact urges customers to use digital banking amidst pandemic Covid-19.

Education Segment

The novel Corona virus (COVID-19) spread across the globe and in India has rung the alarming bells for the education sector in India. It has brought up many upcoming challenges for both the knowledge seekers and teachers in the education industry. The situation has prompted most of the governments to shut down all educational institutions in the country to avoid mass gathering and follow the guidelines of social distancing which according to the research is the most.

COVID 19 & Its Impact on Odisha Economy

The COVID-19 pandemic has dealt a severe blow to the economies at all levels - global, national and regional. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) forecasts that the global output is to contract sharply by -3 percent in 2020, much worse than that during the 2008-09 financial crisis. The advanced economies are set to witness a much larger contraction in output by - 6.1 percent and emerging and market economies by -1 percent. It further warns that the risks would be severe and substantial. For India, different agencies have provided varying growth estimates for 2020-21. The IMF has projected it to be 1.9 percent; Fitch Ratings has forecast 0.8 per cent growth. In early April, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) had forecast a 4 per cent growth for India. Rangarajan and Srivastav have estimated 4.4 per cent growth for India in 2019-20 and 2.94 per cent in 2020-21. The professional forecasters' projection of real GDP growth given in the monetary policy report of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) released in April 2020 reports 4.6 per cent growth in the last quarter of 2019-20, 4.7 per cent in the first quarter, 5.3 per cent in the second quarter, 5.7 per cent in third quarter and 6.1 per cent in the fourth quarter. However, given the length of complete lockdown in India and suspension of most of the economic activities in the first quarter, it is hard to believe that the Indian economy would be able to achieve any growth in 2020-21. There is serious apprehension that the total national output would contract drastically in the first quarter, although there could be some improvement in the subsequent quarters; growth of total output would not be higher than that in the last year. Therefore, the fear of a double digit contraction in the output looms large.

Odisha started imposing partial lockdown from March 21 and by March 22 it was extended to the entire state. With the assumption that the lockdown would be relaxed from early June, two months of the first quarter were to fall under the lockdown. Although the state and national governments have relaxed some selected economic

activities in the lockdown 3.0 (starting from May 4), the operation of those sectors is far from normal. Even if the lockdown has been relaxed from mid-May, there would be a lot of restrictions in most of the economic activities. Therefore, the effect of COVID-19 would continue in the second and third quarters. We would expect normal activities towards the fourth quarter. If we look at each sector independently during this fiscal year, agriculture is the least affected compared to all other sectors. The manufacturing and service sectors have emerged the worst-hit sectors due to lockdown. Odisha's export to the world amounts to around 16 per cent of the GSDP. Due to the pandemic this export would be badly affected. The massive unemployment and return of migrant workers from within the country and outside would pull down the purchasing power of the people in the state. Thus, the aggregate demand (internal + external) would decline significantly.

The lockdown suspended almost all economic activities including those concerning factories, construction and transport (rail, road and aviation). There are many signals of the fall in the output in the first quarter. The total power consumption of the country in April 2020 has declined by 22.75 per cent as compared to that in April last year. The core sector output fell by 6.5 per cent in March 2020 with just one week of lockdown in the country. The Gross Direct Tax collection in April had declined by 5.4 per cent. The tax collection by the Income Tax Department in April is the tax collected by the employers for the income of March. Therefore, the income tax collection for the month of April (that would be reflected in May) would show a significant decline in the direct tax collection. This is indicated by the fact that most of the private companies have slashed the salary of employees up to 50 per cent. Even in the public sector, the Union government has frozen the Dearness Allowances for one year. Many state governments have slashed the salary of government employees. The GST collection of states has declined by more than 75 per cent. The Union government has deferred the release of the GST collection data for the month of April. Further, the CMIE data shows that the unemployment rate in the first week of May has gone up to 23.8 percent. Most of the metros in India have come under the red zones, where more than one third of the total output is produced. Due to the massive movement of migrant workers, the number of districts coming under red zones have increased by the day. In this context, it would be unwise to expect any normal operation of economic activities soon. The exponential growth of number of COVID-19 positive cases after the return of migrant workers from other states also indicates that the restrictions may continue in different parts of the state. As per the information provided by the Government of Odisha, as on May 16, around 15 lakh people from Odisha stranded in other states had already registered to return to their native places. On this date 1,33,245 people had already returned to the state. Out of this, more than 55000 workers had returned to Ganjam district alone, mostly from Surat, Gujarat. On May 16 alone, a total of 17855 people had returned to the state. Twenty lakh migrant workers implies approximately those many families in Odisha are going to be affected due to loss of employment and income. With a very conservative estimate, if we assume that all these migrant workers used to send remittances of minimum ₹ 10000 (average of both migrants working abroad and in other

Indian states) per month, then remittances worth ₹1500 crore would stop flowing to the state every month; or, in a year ₹18000 crore (which amounts to 3.7 per cent of the GSDP or 12 per cent of the state's total budget). Stoppage of flow of this remittance would drastically reduce the demand in the local economy and, hence, slow down growth of the economy. All these signal a drastic fall in the total output and income in the country during the first quarter of 2020-21. Therefore, we strongly presume that instead of any growth the Indian economy would witness a slump in the total output.

A Policy Framework for Economic Revival

Going by the intensity, amplitude and impact of the current pandemic (called now as the 'Great Lockdown' or the 'Great Covid Crisis') it has been compared by informed observers to similar catastrophic events in the global history - the Great Depression of the 1930s and the Great Recession of 2008. In the past, for such economic disasters causes had to be discovered and there emerged several theories, and to some extent that delayed managing and resolving the crises. In case of the COVID-19 pandemic the core of the crisis is identified as an unprecedented public health emergency, and the consequences have been severe damage to well-being, employment and income across nations. Longterm solution depends on how and when we come out of the emergency with a vaccine, available over the counter (OTC) everywhere that restrains COVID19 as any other flu. It is now clear that this is not going to be very soon or even in the near future. Meanwhile, we will have to build a socially-distanced, mask-wearing economy wherein people are employed to produce output from the existing capacity and they are given sufficient income to consume the same output. The principles we know from macroeconomics are clear. It is the fiscal policy that should come to the rescue. Monetary policy should support and become conducive, rather than take the lead. Secondly, the crisis should be appreciated as a true unprecedented uncertainty, warranting principles of 'uncertainty management', rather than 'risk management'. No insurance company could have saved us, and people and economies just do not have a coping mechanism. It is a novel phenomenon and we are all taken by surprise. The response, therefore, should be that of a massive compensation to the poor and job losers for the loss of their income and employment, and widespread bailout of the enterprises, particularly the MSMEs, both in the public and private sectors, in Odisha and elsewhere. However, those should not reduce our abilities now and act as roadblocks on our path of restoring the economy and rebuilding the trust and confidence of people with socioeconomic institutions. Once we stand confidently with good health and income in the near term, we can always bend to apply balms on the wounds. Scars are, of course, permanent and will ever remain, and the economy will never be the same again. The responses should have different time horizons. The short-term measures should be able to restore the economy. In the medium-term we must repair and in the long-run we must revitalize the economy of Odisha. It should be noted that the fiscal and monetary policy response of a State is different from that of a country in a federal set-up. Near-term response As the responsive and well-prepared state government has recognized it early on, the crucial policy issue would be to develop mechanisms to accelerate provision of basic healthcare services to these workers and also carrying out

necessary tests to rule out infections due COVID-19. Health concerns would have to take precedence over employment and income generation approaches by the State. The Government of Odisha should first prevail upon the Union government to convene a virtual meeting of the Union Finance Minister and RBI Governor with the CMs and State Finance Ministers. Odisha should demand and the central authorities should permit a higher fiscal deficit target. In other words, we may miss the targets for some years. Odisha should be permitted to borrow liberally from the RBI. The State should have permission to arrange/negotiate for loan/ aid from international agencies. There should be clear delineation of activities, schemes and bailouts of the centre and the states, and all overlapping spending should be carefully avoided. Odisha should also examine the possibility of increasing State taxes (like State Excise) right from the current year depending on the elasticity and strength of the tax bases. In any case, the value of the money saved by not paying the taxes will automatically be lost in due course to inflation, which is hidden taxation. The money borrowed and resources mobilised should be liberally spent to compensate at least 70 per cent of loss of income of wage-earners, farmers, small businesses, self-help groups and self-employed people in the next three months. The delivery of these compensations through quick-response schemes/packages should be the next most important activity of the district administrations. If necessary, some quick surveys may be undertaken within a fortnight. Medium-term measures The Government of Odisha should demand COVID-19 Surcharges on income tax, mineral royalty and railway transportation of minerals for the next five years The 15th Finance Commission should be urged to examine and appreciate the efforts and requirements of the different states. It is important to maintain and promote the emergency health infrastructure created to deal with COVID-19. Long-term vision This is not the appropriate time to plan for a long-term future of the postCOVID-19 society of Odisha. However, it is difficult to avoid some reflection on the long-term vision. Health, education, people's security through policing, environment and other social sectors are issues of primary focus of a modern welfare state. The future political attention of Odisha should be on these deserving sectors. As per the NITI Aayog Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) India Index Baseline report [21], 32.59 per cent of population in Odisha is below the poverty line as against the national average of 21.92 per cent. The COVID19 pandemic has accentuated the economic crisis in the State where a large segment of its population has been deprived of employment and income opportunities and have exhausted their savings. The Scheduled Tribe population constitutes about 23 per cent of the total population of Odisha and they have been marginalized and poor. They have been deprived of or have limited access to their vital source of livelihood, namely, the land, forests and common property resources (CPR). It is suggested that ownership and control of land by the rural poor is indispensable not only for enhancing their livelihood, food security and social status, but also for improving access to credit markets and security. The Government needs to ensure effective implementation and strict enforcement of land reform measures of re-distributing the surplus lands among the landless tribes. This would encourage local tribes to pursue various natural resource-based activities

as livelihood pursuits. Consequent upon job losses and a complete shutdown of economic activities, it is essential to provide for food supply and basic necessities for survival and ensure cash transfers to the vulnerable poor, tribes, migrants, landless manual workers. The most important driving force of an economy is to generate aggregate effective demand of non-food items so as to generate productive activities in industries and services sector. Expedient implementation of the PM-JAY or Ayushman Bharat scheme, claiming of speedy release of the pending Goods and Services Tax (GST) to Odisha, assisting the underprivileged self-employed to kick-start their enterprises and (ii) reviving MSMEs, hospitality, transport and other industries soon will go a long way to mitigate the adverse effects of the pandemic. The Government of Odisha -- recognized at the international arena for its distinctive crisis management -- has moved ahead with investment plans to generate employment with maximum linkage effects. A total of six investment proposals amounting to ₹ 9,100 crore were cleared by the Government of Odisha to bring the battered economy back on track amid the COVID-19 pandemic which is expected provide employment to over 6,500 people in the state having its multiplier effects on employment and income too. As we were pushed into the crisis, it was 'life' that took a priority and rightly so. But after three months it is equally important to reconstruct and revive livelihoods to sustain lives, while not ignoring the health issues. The governments step to rev up the health care issues and ensure that all rural households and all households from urban slums will be visited by ASHA workers and ANM workers from 16 June to 31 July 2020 is a welcome step in the direction. And simultaneously efforts to kick start the economy must be prioritized.

Effective way to check the spread

The education sector of India is deeply uprooted with student. Teacher learning by means and ways of classroom interaction but the global pandemic has forced both students and teachers to move to technology based virtual learning. The adaptation to this change in methodology of both teaching and learning has posed a great challenge for the education sector. Educators and students had experienced a ripple effect of the Corona virus as universities, colleges, schools were closed in the country. The virus had a more severe consequence for the educational institutions which did not have the support of online learning platforms. The radical shift from classroom education to online education has benefitted only a small portion of the society due to lack of availability of resources supporting online education, the most affected being the poor. This had brought a lot of disruptions in the academic calendar and financial process of many institutions. Also, UNESCO has reported that COVID—19 has disturbed the education of about 290.5 million students across the global and somehow has created a phase of unemployment for some teachers.

Summary & Conclusion:

The entire world is in the grip of vicious corona virus. The pandemic outbreak has sparked a global health emergency along with social and economic crisis unleashing unprecedented collapse of the economic activities and business operations, It has severe repercussions on the global business world. Therefore, this study has put forward the potential effects of corona virus on the

different sectors of Indian Economy. This is high time to reset everything as the world has become standstill for a few months due to the outbreak of Covid-19. We all are allowed to rethink, redesign, and restructure everything. If we involve in doing the right things, we may be able to fix challenges in new platforms that can face and bear humankind's environmental damage, may be it pollution, self-centered growth or inequality, or concentration of economic power and wealth.

The Government of Odisha has been successful in controlling the spread of COVID-19 in the state by taking various proactive policy measures. Since the last week of April, with the return of migrant workers, the number of confirmed cases of COVID-19 has spiked in the state. However, most of these cases have been found in the quarantine centers. The State is gradually moving towards community spread of the virus. At this stage the Sarpanch and elected representatives of ULBs can play a very important role in educating the local people. The State is gradually opening up the economy to save livelihoods and generate income for its citizens. The government has announced a slew of packages for the returnee-migrant workers, farmers and wage earners in urban areas. However, this will not be sufficient to revive the economy and generate employment opportunities for the unemployed youth. The State Government should design special policy measures to create employment opportunities for the semi-skilled and skilled youths by setting up rural enterprises in every Panchayat and ULB. The COVID-19 crisis has exposed the limited capacity of the healthcare infrastructure in the State, which needs to at least double the spending in the health sector. Every district of Odisha should have a medical college with sufficient manpower and adequate infrastructure. Recent times have shown that virus generated pandemics are affecting the humanity with alarming frequency. Hence testing facilities must be made available at least at CHCs to help control and contain the situation. The education system of the state is not equipped to face the challenges of the digital and knowledge economy. All schools, colleges and universities need to be equipped with IT infrastructure for online learning. All teachers from schools, colleges and universities need to be trained to generate online study materials. For reopening schools and colleges, the State needs to move with caution. Most of the educational institutions in several advanced countries have announced their closure till the end of 2020. Given the fact that the number of positive cases are spiking in the State and will continue for some more time, there should not be any hurry to reopen schools, colleges and universities.

The state government can start classes through TV channels and radios which can reach maximum number of students. For the effective management of the COVID-19 crisis decentralized efforts are needed. All the PRIs and ULBs of the state need to be empowered with more funds, functions and functionaries. In line with the NDRF and SDRF, all PRIs and ULBs should have a disaster relief fund for swiftly responding to the disasters. Due to lockdown, the global GDP and the GDP of India is set to contract. Many agencies have also warned for a double digit contraction in India's GDP. Odisha's GSDP may also contract between 13 to 16 percent during 2020-21. Agriculture and allied activities and mining activities would be the savior for the State during 2020-21. Therefore, the State Government

needs to provide all inputs free of cost for the kharif season. Due to the lockdown, the revenue collection of the State may decline, so also the transfer of funds from the Union Government under share taxes to the tune of ₹ 11313 crore. While at the same time the State cannot contract the expenditures because the economy has to be revived. Some amount of capital expenditure can be shifted towards health sectors. The State Government may consider not starting new schemes and, instead, redirect those funds towards providing income and livelihood support. In this context, if the State aims to spend at least the amount proposed in the budget, it needs to increase the borrowing limit to between 6 and 8 per cent of the GSDP. Therefore, the state needs to submit a memorandum to the Union Government and the 15th Finance Commission to relax the FRBM limits for at least two years

We think the most significant point is that we must ensure and make the best of efforts that this black phase of life should never happen with all of us again. I am sure that humankind has never taken lassos and wisdom from history. Let's hope for the better, healthy, safe, prosperous, and of course, sustainable future ahead.

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